

MANAGEMENT OF THE PEDAGOGICAL TEAM IN GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar kizi

"TIIAME"NRU researcheradmin

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10102961>

Abstract. *In the era of modern educational reforms, the issue of managing the pedagogical team in general secondary schools is one of the issues that should be emphasized. Because the effective management of the pedagogical team affects the quality of education. In this regard, this article was created.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, improving staff, quality of education, education system.*

One of the most important tasks and strategic goals of the educational institution is the development of the teaching staff teaching pupils or students in educational institutions as the most relevant topics of the present day. Due to the modernization of the education management system, it is necessary to constantly pay attention to changes in the behavior of teachers and management staff. Today, as reforms are being carried out at all levels of the education system, the transfer of financial responsibility from the top level to the regional level, the unification of educational institutions, and as a result of this, the urgency of management will increase.

The problems of training, education and management of an educational institution are among the problems that require a systematic, activity-based and person-oriented approach. Today, in the conditions of student-oriented education, the educational process has acquired its own semantic meaning and technological outline. The system-creating factor of the pedagogical system is management, which is the art of managing the educational process and, in particular, the educational and cognitive activities of students, pedagogical management, that is, a set of principles, methods, organizational forms, and technological techniques. These are very important for managing the educational process, which contributes to its effectiveness and quality.

In today's developing world, pedagogical activity has an active social position, and it requires purposeful implementation of the tasks of raising the level of education of leaders. The management process always takes place in the process of the joint activity of people to achieve certain results. In modern schools, the rational relationship between the head of the school and the pedagogical team requires certain professional competencies of both parties in the management process.

In independent countries that are going through an economic transition period, there is a need to modernize the education system, as in all areas. After all, it is impossible to supply professional personnel to new industrial sectors of the economy without modernization of education. Modernization of the education system begins with general secondary schools. It is impossible to change the educational environment in the school without reforming the school management system. Therefore, it is now possible to create a modern school model by applying advanced foreign management models to the school management system based on national interests. The most important direction of modernization of the education system is to change the management model of the system. The immediate goal is to develop an optimal management model with clearly distributed and coordinated powers, functions and responsibilities of all subjects of education policy.

Taking into account the clearly defined definition of the educational system as a social institution and a type of social system, it is appropriate to use general approaches of social management to solve the problems of their management. Within this concept, management is interpreted as the influence of the subject on the object of management and implies the optimization of processes during the purposeful transition of the educational system from one state to another.

If a person does not develop, he begins to lose his existing skills. Similarly, in order to maintain and develop schools in the rapidly changing world, the head of the school and his pedagogical team should acquire modern competencies. Creation of modern professional competences in the leader and pedagogical team, improvement of their continuous qualification is a necessary condition for the development of the school. The success of any organization depends on the competence of the team. There are two ways to build a strong team — hire more professional educators or develop existing educators to grow them gradually.

In the countries of the former Soviet Union, which gained their independence in the 90s of the 20th century, due to the high dependence of education on the Soviet ideology, the development of education was not given serious attention in the closed economy. Young independent countries have experienced a difficult economic transition period. As a result of the closure of the economy, the disconnection of economic relations with other countries of the national economies acting as a raw material base, the sharp decrease in economic growth has led to a sharp decrease in the financial resources allocated to social spheres, including education. During the transition period, many independent countries did not pay serious attention to education. The management of general secondary education schools was not much different from the management system of the old system.

Currently, the concept of management is spreading from the business sphere to various spheres of human activity, as well as to education. However, the concept of management is narrower than the concept of management, because management mainly refers to various aspects of the leader's activity, while the concept of management covers the entire field of human relations in "manager-executive" systems. Thus, the theory of school management, in particular, the pedagogical team, is significantly complemented by the theory of intra-school management. Evidence of this can be seen in the views and researches of Yu.A. Konarzhevsky, T.I. Shamova and others.

The effectiveness of management activities of general education schools is determined to a large extent by how school leaders master the methodology of pedagogical analysis, how deeply they study the identified facts and identify the most characteristic connections. Untimely or unprofessional analysis of the activity of the school director leads to uncertainty and sometimes unreasonableness of the decisions made at the stage of goal development and task formation. Ignorance of the actual state of work in the pedagogical or student, student community creates difficulties in establishing the correct system of relations during the process of regulating and correcting the pedagogical process.

The main goal of pedagogical analysis as a management function is to study the state and development trends of the pedagogical process, objectively evaluate its results, and then develop recommendations for regulating the managed system. This function is one of the most time-consuming functions in the structure of the control cycle, because the analysis involves dividing

the parts of the object under study into a single whole, establishing relationships between the factors that make up the system.

The problem of managing pedagogical personnel in general education schools is primarily related to increasing the efficiency of educating the young generation in our schools in the context of the transition to a market economy. The issue of education and upbringing is characteristic of each era. Even today, the need for competitive labor resources is high for independent countries. The effectiveness of education and upbringing can be achieved only by properly establishing the school management system. Since the school is a social organization, it is a system of joint activity of people (teachers, students, parents), it is appropriate to carry out scientific research on the development of effective management mechanisms.

In addition, it is a very important issue in this process to provide managers, principals, and school managers who perform leadership duties in comprehensive schools with mature knowledge and demonstrate management skills. Since these qualities are present, the school manager can correctly choose the methods of managing the pedagogical team and correctly assess the relationship with them in professional processes. This, of course, has a positive effect on the effectiveness of the quality of education. Because for every teacher working in the educational system, it can be said that the attitude, attention and encouragement of the leader who leads him acts as a motivation to organize meaningful and high-quality educational processes.

REFERENCES

1. Jalilova D. Ta'lim jarayonlarining samaradorligini oshirish uchun innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ahamiyati. "Sifatli ta'lim - tarag'givot povdevori" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to'plami // Toshkent, 2023-yil 20-aprel. 282-286-betlar.
2. Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. THE IMPORTANCE OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING DESIGN ABILITY IN PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 566-569p.
3. Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 451-452-453p.
4. Гришина И. В., Волков В. Н., Анализ особенностей управленческой деятельности руководителя школы в современных условиях. Научные сообщения. Научно-теоритический журнал. 2019. (Grishina I. V., Volkov V. N., Analysis of the features of the managerial activity of the head of the school in modern conditions).
5. S Mirkhayitova, G Shodiyeva, M Irmatova. Teaching creative thinking to secondary school students through independent education is a pressing issue ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 10 (8), 26-31.
6. https://t.me/jalilova_dilshoda_2292
7. https://t.me/ilmiy_yordam_beraman
8. <https://cyberleninka.ru>
9. <http://scientists.uz>